

Instructions board game: “Jury Trials (Green v Blue)”

1. Instructions for printing it out

Please use A4 sized paper to print out cards. Print more than one copy as needed, e.g., if there are more than 6 player cards.

2. Aim of the game

This game is a role-playing game designed for people with a background or interest in law and data privacy. The context of the game is around defending a company’s public image against attackers who try to destroy its reputation in a specific scenario case present. Participants are divided into two teams: the blue team attacks the strategies of the company trying to harm its public image whereas the green team tries to defend the image of the company and its measures. The solutions and arguments of both teams will be accessed by the jury members who will determine the winners based on how well they defended or attacked the company. This is set in a universe where companies must defend against attackers who try to destroy their reputation in an eternal struggle between Green and Blue to defend their strategies and their trustworthiness and transparency. The goal is to learn about data privacy and legal issues from the requirements prompts and information sheet, and then to discuss the complexity surrounding how they affect trust and transparency. For example, one team may have a solid more technical strategy, but the other team is more persuasive about the effects to data subjects and the Jury can award the point to either team, as long as they explain the reasoning (e.g., Jury A is impressed by the technical strategy, while Jury B is concerned for data subjects and is persuaded more). As the Jury may be quite subjective, players have the chance to switch roles after one round and understand different perspectives. There are various opportunities to change teams and multiple win conditions based on how much time is allotted and how many points are needed.

Duration:

30min or more

Player Characters:

- Jury Member (judges the teams)
- Green team (Players for the company aka “defenders”)
- Blue team (Players against the company aka “attackers”)

3. What’s Included?

Game elements and descriptions:

- Definition of scenarios
 - Defines terms of the scenario
- Requirement Information table

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- Gives background information about the requirements
- Jury vs Player cards
 - These determine if someone is playing as a jury member of a player. Jury members judge the strategies from the Green and Blue team and determine a winner per round.
- Green vs Blue team cards
 - Of the players, these determine who is on the Green team (developing a strategy to achieve the requirement card prompt) and Blue team (breaking down the strategy from the green team)
- Scenario cards
 - These describe the company and issues they are facing. The teams must tailor their responses to the prompts, such as the types of challenges they are facing and should be addressed.
- Requirement cards
 - These cards cover different goals that the team's strategy should try to achieve.
- Instruction cards
 - These give general instructions for the game and teams. They can remind players of the rules of the game.

4. How to play

Initial phase:

1. Decide on the number of Jury members. There must be an odd number of Jury members. Guidelines: If there are only 5 players, then there is one Jury member who takes all the Jury role cards. If there are 9+ players, then there can be 3 Jury members. Choose the appropriate number of Jury member cards for the number of players and shuffle with blank "player" cards.
2. Split the players into Green or Blue teams. Select an equal number of Green and Blue team cards and shuffle. Each player chooses a card to decide teams.
3. The Jury selects a scenario from the list of existing scenarios to set the scene. See Definitions sheet if needed.

Turn phase:

1. Green team players go first to draw a requirements card. They then have 5min to read the information related to the requirements card and 5min to build a strategy to address requirements. The cards have prompts that players should answer, and players can approach it more technically or socially (based on presentation and confidence), as long as they try to win over the Jury.

IMPORTANT: some requirements cards only apply to one scenario; the correspondence is stated in the Information Table. Draw again if the requirements card is for the other scenario.

2. Blue team players against the company take notes on the Green team's strategy and can ask questions from the Green team for 5min. Then they have to build an adversarial strategy in 5min They should review the requirement card's prompt and see how they can attack the Green team's strategy for fulfilling that requirement. Did they fulfil the requirement? Are there holes in their strategy that do not completely address the prompt? This can be more about the content, the presentation, even ad hominem attacks on the other team, as long as they try to win over the Jury.
3. The Jury has 2min to deliberate and chooses a winner, then explains why for up to 3 minutes. A decision is subjective, but as long as it is explained their ruling is the final word. They may award the point to the most persuasive, confident team or the team with a solid, technical answer. They keep track of the score.

That completes one round of the game.

If playing a second round, for the second round players may change roles. Repeat any of the initialization phase required to create new teams or Jury members.

Then, the Green turn begins, followed by the Blue, then the Jury.

Win conditions!

There can be several win conditions based on the time of play.

- One round: short ~30min game where the team who receives the Jury vote wins
- Three rounds: longer ~90min game where the team who receives 3 Jury votes wins

5. Scenarios

- Toomtoom is a medium-sized marketplace company that is trying to gain a larger foothold in the market. They follow current trends for data security (ISO standards), AI for showing personalized ads, and informed consent that use dark patterns to get more customers. While it is a grey area for being legally compliant given that everyone follows

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the same dark patterns (like where it is more clicks to refuse consent than give consent) they are considering building brand loyalty by positioning themselves as an extremely trustworthy and transparent company. Toomtoom now seeks to understand if this public trust can be built with dark patterns or if it is worth putting in extra effort to get rid of dark patterns.

- Hoggle Inc., a leading technology company, has implemented a machine learning algorithm for its hiring process. The algorithm, designed to identify the most suitable candidates, inadvertently leads to the hiring of significantly more women than men. This outcome arises because the algorithm heavily weighs a particular feature, "collaborative skills," which, due to various social and educational factors, is more commonly exhibited in the profiles of female candidates. This has led to a disproportionate hiring of women over men, even though the protected attribute (sex) was not used to train the hiring system. Hoggle Inc. now seeks to understand whether their perceived public trust will be affected by this practice and guidance on their next steps.

6. Scenario's Definitions

Toomtoom definitions:

Dark Pattern – A dark pattern is a way something can be purposefully designed to trick users into doing things, such as buying a hotel room because there is a ticking timer, or having a colorful button to give cookie consent that is more eye-catching than the button to refuse consent.

ISO standard- These are security standards and protocols set by the International Organization for Standardization which has expert representatives from a wide range of member countries.

AI- Stands for artificial intelligence, in which a machine or algorithm is designed to perform high level tasks, such as recognizing someone's interests and serving advertisements relevant to them.

Hoggle Inc. Definitions:

Algorithmic Fairness – Group similarity in outcomes based on a protected attribute.

Biases – Deviations from group similarity in outcome.

Direct Discrimination - Direct discrimination occurs where one person is treated less favorably on grounds of prohibited criterion (racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age, sexual orientation or sex) than another is, has been or would be treated in a comparable situation.

Indirect Discrimination - Indirect discrimination takes place when a neutral provision, criterion, or practice results in a disparate impact on a protected group, unless that provision, criterion or practice is objectively justified by a legitimate aim and the means of achieving that aim are appropriate and necessary.

7. Information Table (refer to your requirements card)

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<u>Scenario</u>	<u>Requirement Card</u>	<u>Information</u>
Hogle	Fairness Through Unawareness	Art. 21 of the European Charter of Fundamental Rights; Art. 1-7 of Council Directive 2000/78/EC of 27 November 2000 establishing a general framework for equal treatment in employment and occupation. (both printed-out and highlighted for ease)
Hogle	Fairness Through Awareness	Essentially, fairness through awareness is the use of the protected attribute to constrain the outcomes of the automated system in line with group similarity in outcome. In the Hogle scenario, doing so would produce a trade-off between accuracy and fairness. (key slides on FTA will be shared in the packet from: https://course.ece.cmu.edu/~ece734/fall2013/lectures/cmu13-fairness.pdf)
Hogle	Feature Audit	Once the outputs of the hiring systems are audited, since they have identified the disparity in outcomes between sexes, the weighting of features responsible for such disparities might be reconsidered.
Hogle	Fairness	Associations/correlations between two or more variables may encode the value/information about another variable. Thus, ensuring full independence between variables is a hard task. Plus, those correlations may even be used to run effective attacks against some privacy-enhancing techniques such as differential privacy.
Hogle	Privacy Vs fairness	Many fairness techniques oblige/constrain models to learn from groups of data that were originally discriminated against. Forcing models to learn from insufficient poorly represented groups of data leads models to memorize those data points to achieve the goal of performing well in these groups, however, this memorization can be exploited by attackers to easily reveal those data points since models memorize them thus their extraction is easier. This problem makes these under-represented groups face a disproportioned risk of leakage.
Toomtoom	Privacy against other users	Users of recommendation systems may use the recommenders' outputs to maintain leakage attacks that can reconstruct or even reveal the data of certain other users whose data were used to train or update these recommendation systems (recommendation systems are periodically updated and retrained to ensure their quality).
Both	Privacy	When training big and large models the companies may use third-party servers such as Amazon sageMaker to train these models due to the need to have big computational resources. Thus, training data needs to be sent to these servers. The servers will then retain full copies of the training data with no technical guarantees that these data won't be used for other purposes and no means to audit these third parties about the usage of the datasets that they retain on their servers after training.

Both	Security Threats	Before deciding to apply any security of privacy solution, engineers and managers should build threat models enumerating all the parties involved in the data flow, the threatening parties and the protected ones, the available resources, and desired outcomes. These threat models are the way to check whether a given security strategy succeeds or not in meeting the requirements of these threat models.
Both	Training	Companies and projects have multidisciplinary teams working on them; thus, each team comes with a different background of knowledge. This diversity makes the training for aspects of privacy, transparency and other requirements challenging for all teams.
Both	Communication is Blind	There is lots of research about how little privacy policies describing data processing are read, given that they can be long, vague, and not written for a general audience. Most people have probably never read one in their life! A consent form may also try to explain the data processing that consent is needed for, but it can be difficult to explain the purpose and research also shows that many people do not often have the background to weigh the risks and benefits, but make decisions based on expectations of privacy, risks, and benefits.
Both	Jargon or Overkill?	Even if someone wants to read a privacy policy or consent form to understand how data is processed, often it can be written legalese to cover legal requirements. While it may be approved by a lawyer, the terms can be confusing. They may use lots of vague terms to cover many scenarios, but then it is unclear what is happening. Additionally, policies may be endless and full of technical jargon e.g., a 50+ long list of companies that will be sent your data, or details about how it will be used for a specific type of machine learning algorithm to improve services that someone would only understand with training.
Toomtoom	Legal Manipulation	<p>The Digital Services Act (DSA) is an EU regulation that states providers of online platforms (such as online marketplaces, app stores, collaborative economy platforms and social media platforms). They give examples such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • giving unequal visual prominence to any options when asking the user for a decision (a form of misdirection technique). • repetitively requesting or urging the receipting to make a decision such as repeatedly requesting consents to data processing where consent has previously been refused (especially in the form of a pop-up that interferes with the user experience) or has been refused through the use of automatic refusal configurations.

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		<p>However, in practice this can be hard to implement, as there are very few “neutral” designs.</p> <p>Following a regulation, the enforcement of any violations is paramount. This will set a precedence. However, the regulation is very new, and no public decisions have yet to be made. Thus, many dark patterns may still be in a grey area until a case is brought up in court.</p>
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